

SALES PROMOTION WITH REFERENCE TO YAMAHA MOTOR

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ABSTRACT

The Indian vehicle industry has created and since 1898, when the vehicle has contacted the boulevards of India just because. At present, the world's tenth position on the subsequent floor is separated into two haggles in business vehicles. By building up a development rate of 18% per annum and a yearly creation of more than 2million units, it may not be overstated to state that this industry in past years will shroud 10 million units every year. Notwithstanding the development in India's monetary framework, India's white collar class extension has likewise been a noteworthy job to depict when assembling universal autos to the Indian Automotive Market. With everything taken into account, India is one of the countries that gives talented work at lower cut costs that make their very own assembling focuses better. India's market attraction and the advancement of worldwide vehicle industry, for example, Japan, Europe, and the US have caused new aggregate occasions alongside huge capital interest in the part.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Indian Two-Wheeler Industry

India is the second one-largest maker on the earth and the world's biggest manufacturer. For the maximum part Indian shoe enterprise has created towards the finish of time. The Indian motorbike industry started out in the fifth century. Car India (API) items have started to make bicycles inside the country. Cycle is a chunk of the Indian biking enterprise, the alternative is motorcycle and sulked. The first india affiliation is some of the greatest bicycle makers on this planet. Saints of Toyota and Bajaj Auto are two huge Indian institutions and fill the vehicle association. Notwithstanding the endeavors attempted, numerous Japanese undertakings at the bicycle, and Japanese institutions. Indian manual associations currently make -wheeled arrangements, for instance, Step-Through and Scooters. This has been despatched by way of joining motorcycle wheels. Outer associations have started a further bike in India.

1.2 COMPANY PROFILE

Automobile enterprise is one of the better companies on earth. Going in order to a considerable aspect plus aspect that effects within actual lifestyles, it can make the monetary bit of the particular world's maximum overwhelming nation. In India, the automobile company has been growing quick for the reason that will improvement of the automobile business and the two noteworthy wheels marketed.

Development continues to be damaged and will be also precluded from actual and authority redistributing. The particular outcome turned into after that attempted with the help of a faraway gamer to the Indian marketplace. Wheeler's phase become delivered via Indian Vehicles (API) and Enfield matters thru the 50's. After the maximum latest years, Bajaj Autos started out building up a Vespa bicycle from the Piaggio German affiliation. For a long term, the vehicle commercial enterprise in India is known for its bicycles with the API and Bajaj along the market enterprise. There are numerous open things and alternatives, for example, machines, and Enfield and Rajdoot are showcased. The 80s comprehended the surge of Japanese institutions within the Indian marketplace through opening markets for far off associations. Honda's number one characters and TVS Suzuki associations are available at the season of market change. Generally the marketplace may be overwhelmed via bikes and Bajaj and LML are the brands that produce products round that time. Bicycle is available seen common circle of relatives and with a vehicle that may be taken into consideration as cruisers just as alongside those strains.

Yamaha Motor India Pvt. Restricted. (YMI) is a very backup of YMC and fills in as place of work at domestic and control assortment of Indian commercial enterprise duties business for YMC. YMI is within payment of Business Planning and Strategy, Company Planning and Business Growth and High quality and Conformity Assurance from Yamaha Indian Business.

Yamaha Motor Indian Sales Pvt. Ltd. (YMIS) is a backup of YMC. YMIS turned into based by YMC to present Product sales and Marketing groups to IYM. At the office at home in Chennai, YMIS bolsters IYM to market and promote cruisers and motorcycles in near by and fare markets.

Yamaha Engine R and d Indian Pvt. Ltd. (YMRI) is an auxiliary of YMC. YMRI started out by YMC to present R and D and item enhancement administrations for IYM. Basis camp in Surajpur, GautamBudh Nagar (U. P.), YMRI grows new items for IYM for household and fare markets. YMRI is the fifth household workplace of the T and D in Phazer Motor Group in Italia, Taiwan, China, and Asian countries.

2.RESEARCH DESIGN

2.1 STATEMENT OF THJE PROBLEM

This particular examination is a mix of explorative and elegant procedures that lead looking at and perception to learn about sellers and correspondences to react to clients. This is a cross-sectional examination led in June and July.

For consumer loyalty examine a detailed survey containing 17 shut inquiry addresses that are conveyed for reaction by means of the web and essentially through private client interviews at Yamaha businesses. This information is then created utilizing SPSS through cross-execution in different factors. The consequences of this progression structure the premise of the suggestions given to the organization.

To think about Yamaha's notoriety and deals advancement in the cruiser showcase, chose statistics registration and all business propelled in the Far East, Mosaram Auto Sales (Honda Hero), I led a market review by getting an open meeting with merchants and market marches

2.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To comprehend client observations about the dispatch of the new FZ and FZS bicycle Yamaha.
- To decide your clients' fulfillment about your bicycle and after deals administration.
- To decide the components that influence the purchaser decision about bikes
- To find out about the second bike industry advertise situation

2.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This investigation is gone for giving India Yamaha Motors understanding into FZ and FZS accomplishment just as client reaction and familiarity with Yamaha brands, items and administrations.

The information has been investigated and displayed in a basic and exact way on a recommended premise made for better corporate administrations, arrangements and systems in India.

2.4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The reports are composed based on data gathered from various sources. To locate the correct research venture object, apply. In the wake of giving a mind assault session, the object is chosen and set based on that objective. A poll is principally a noteworthy accentuation that gathers thoughts or bits of knowledge into deciding and coding an answer for the issue.

3. DATA ANALYSIS& INTERPRETATION

3.1 WHAT IS YOUR OCCUPATION?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Student	20	40
Office Employee	14	28
Factory Employee	06	12
Shop Owner	10	20
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the occupation of the student is 40%,Office Employee is 28% ,Factory Employee is 12% and Shop Owner is 20%.

3.2 WHAT IS YEAR HOUSE HOLD INCOME?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
UP TO Rs 10,000	2	04
Rs 10,001-20,000	14	28
Rs 20,001-40,000	25	50
Rs 40,001-ABOVE	09	18
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year house hold income of the Up to Rs 10,000 is 4%,Rs 10,001 – 20,000 is 28% ,Rs 20,001-40,00 is 50% and above 40,001 is 18%.

3.3 HOW DID YOU BUY THE MOTOR CYCLE?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
CASH	27	54
LOAN	23	46
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the how did you buy the motor cycle with Cash is 54% and with Loan is 46%.

3.4 WHO PAID FOR YOUR MOTORCYCLE?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
SELF	28	56
FAMILY	22	44
OTHERS	00	00
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the self 56% Family 42% others 0%

3.5 DID YOU CONSIDERED OTHER MOTORCYCLE WHILE BUYING THIS MODEL?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
YES	27	54
NO	23	46
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the yes 54% No 46%

3.6 WHICH MODEL DID YOU COMPARE WITH? MODEL

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	25	50
NO	25	50
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 50% No 50%

3.7 HAVE YOU SEEN FZ16 TVCF?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	42	84
NO	8	16
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the yes 84% No 16%

3.8 HAVE YOU SEEN FZ16 NEWS PAPER ADVERTISEMENT?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	39	78
NO	11	22
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 78% No 22%

3.9 DO YOU TAKE INFORMATION FROM INTERNET BLOGS?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	44	88
NO	6	12
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 88% No 12%

3.10 DO YOU THINK YAMAHA HAS IMPROVED AFTER FZS AND R15?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	39	78
NO	11	22
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 78% No 22%

3.11 HOW DOES YOUR FRIEND SAY TO YOUR MOTOR CYCLE?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
TRENDY	17	34
STYLISH	32	64
LOW MILEAGE	1	2
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Trendy 34% Stylish 64% Low Mileage 2%

3.12 DID THEY DELIVER YOUR VEHICLE ON TIME?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	38	76
NO	12	24
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPETATION: For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 76% No 24%

4.FINDING,CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

4.1 FINDING

- For the above questionnaire shown that the occupation of the student is 40%,Office Employee is 28% ,Factory Employee is 12% and Shop Owner is 20%.
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year house hold income of the Up to Rs 10,000 is 4%,Rs 10,001 – 20,000 is 28% ,Rs 20,001-40,00 is 50% and above 40,001 is 18%.

- For the above questionnaire shown that the how did you buy the motor cycle with Cash is 54% and with Loan is 46%.
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the self 56% Family 42% others 0%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the yes 54% No 46%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 50% No 50%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the yes 84% No 16%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 78% No 22%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 88% No 12%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 78% No 22%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Trendy 34% Stylish 64% Low Mileage 2%
- For the above questionnaire shown that the year of the Yes 76% No 24%

4.2 SUGGESTIONS

- Abra Motor is notable amidst the madrasah, it must be nearer to Chennai for a superior and bigger. Abra engines need to keep guarantee to clients at the season of conveyance. Abra
- should prepare deals officials by knowing enough information and talents to deal with clients. Abra engines must keep the guarantee that will be guaranteed at the season of conveyance and accomplish client desires. Angra engines need to incorporate quality products to clients at the season of supervision
- and conveyance. Angra engines ought to keep up civility and specifications for the consumer to increase the quality and best supervision. Abra engines ought to be a decent Fiat dealer in Chennai. Angra engine deals power really need to be trusted for clients to steer clear of

- change your image or vendor. Abra engines will increase the promoting mode and upgrade the procedure to attract new clients. Angra engines need to broaden proficiency and development by remaining available.
- Typically the Abra's motorbike development will depend totally on Volkswagen's bargains. Organizations need to completely focus on deals in the quest for client needs. Abra engines desire a whole lot of offer that becomes the top rundown in web crawls
- To be able to draw in new customers, individuals should give better restrictions and rewards for will buy made by clients.

4.3 CONCLUSION

In light of these, special developments are critical to develop the organization's deals plus achieve new business. Each organization must have a good important arrangement for advancements that will can be held within the market with remarkable challenge. The organization's markdown and steadfastness program will certainly expand deals by tugging in new clients. The particular top from the line development will enable the business to accomplish its respected objectives. Deals advancements have to build deals in every association. Deals are examined dependent on special workouts polished by such organizations, organizations ought to possess better limited time workouts drilled in associations in order to assess deals. In this manner, offers advancements assume a substantial work in the association to distinguish the objectives and focuses on of the association. Businesses should structure the greatest vital designs to fulfill market rivalry and fulfill client needs. Numerous makers have demonstrated that company advancements are the secrets that help organizations earn their deals. As pointed out by Philp Austin, "advancement is really a captivating power with regard to the using an object. " This demonstrates specific advancements can empower consumers to purchase items.

REFERENCES

1. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , PERFORMANCE AFFECTING FACTORS OF INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, George Washington International Law Review, Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 607-621, Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrappa-Haralayya.pdf>
2. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY AFFECTING FACTORS IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, Turkish

Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI), Vol.- 12 Issue -03, June 2021, PAGE No : 603-620, Available at: <https://www.tojqi.net/index.php/journal/article/view/791/242>

3. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, George Washington International Law Review, Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 631-642
Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrappa-Haralayya-1.pdf>
4. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL ,STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF BANKS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com) ,Volume: 2, Issue: 5, May 2021, Page No : 184-194. Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2105025.pdf>
5. Bhadrappa Haralayya ; P. S. Aithal . "Study on Model and Camel Analysis of Banking" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals ,Volume 4 ,Issue 11 ,May 2021 Page 244-259. Available at <https://irejournals.com/paper-details/1702750>
6. Bhadrappa Haralayya and Aithal, P. S.. “Analysis of cost efficiency on scheduled commercial banks in India”. International Journal of Current Research, Volume 13, Issue 06, June 2021, pp 17718-17725 Available at: <https://www.journalcra.com/sites/default/files/issue-pdf/41580.pdf>
7. Bhadrappa Haralayya and P. S. Aithal, “A Study On Structure and Growth of Banking Industry in India”, International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management ,Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2021. Page no 225–230. Available at: <https://www.journals.resaim.com/ijresm/article/view/778/749>.
8. Bhadrappa Haralayya, Retail Banking Trends in India ,International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), Volume: 9, Issue: 5, Year: May 2021, Page No : 3730-3732. Available At http://www.ijaresm.com/uploaded_files/document_file/Bhadrappa_Haralayyaqscw.pdf
9. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, FACTORS DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR : A TOBIT REGRESSION ANALYSIS", International Journal of Science & Engineering Development Research (www.ijsdr.org), Vol.6, Issue 6, June-2021, page no.1 - 6, , Available :<http://www.ijsdr.org/papers/IJSDR2106001.pdf>
10. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR

ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, flusserstudies, Volume 30, June 2021,Page No:1068-1080, Available at: <https://flusserstudies.org/archives/801>

11. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS, International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1, June-2021 ,Page no: 159 – 164, Available: http://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT151514_PAPER.pdf
12. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , STUDY OF BANKING SERVICES PROVIDED BY BANKS IN INDIA, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com), Volume: 2, Issue: 6, Year: June 2021,Page No : 06-12, Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2106002.pdf>.
13. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANK PERFORMANCE USING CAMEL APPROACH", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (www.jetir.org | UGC and issn Approved), Vol.8, Issue 5, May-2021, page no 305-314, Available at : <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2105840.pdf>
14. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, ANALYSIS OF BANK PRODUCTIVITY USING PANEL CAUSALITY TEST, Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Volume 50, Issue 6, June-2021 , Page no: 1 – 16, Available at: <https://app.box.com/s/o71lh776opeypauvzucp9esntjwur9zf>
15. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, INTER BANK ANALYSIS OF COST EFFICIENCY USING MEAN, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJIRSET), Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021 ,Page no: 6391-6397, Available at: http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2021/june/97_INTER_NC1.pdf
16. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY MATRIX OF BANKS BY HMTFP AND FPTFP, Science, Technology and Development Journal, Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021, Page no: 190-203, Available at: <http://journalstd.com/gallery/23-june2021.pdf>
17. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY AGGREGATE LEVEL, Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume 13, Issue 6, June- 2021 ,Page no: 296-314, available at: <https://www.xajzkjdx.cn/gallery/28-june2021.pdf>
18. Bhadrappa Haralayya, P S Aithal, "ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR

PRODUCTIVITY BY DISAGGREGATE LEVEL", International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), Volume.9, Issue 6, June 2021, pp.b488-b502, Available at :<http://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2106187.pdf>

19. Haralayya B. Importance of CRM in Banking and Financial Sectors Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021, 6(1): 8-9
20. Haralayya B. How Digital Banking has Brought Innovative Products and Services to India. Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021; 6(1): 16-18
21. Haralayya B. Top 5 Priorities That will Shape The Future of Retail Banking Industry in India. Journal of Advanced Research in HR and Organizational Management 2021; 8(1&2): 17-18.
22. Haralayya B. Millennials and Mobile-Savvy Consumers are Driving a Huge Shift in The Retail Banking Industry. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 17-19
23. Haralayya B. Core Banking Technology and Its Top 6 Implementation Challenges. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 25-27
24. Nitesh S Vibhute ; Dr. Chandrakant B. Jewargi ; Dr. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Non-Performing Assets of Public Sector Banks" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals Volume 4, Issue, 12 June 2021, Page 52-61 Available at <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702767.pdf>
25. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa and Saini, Shrawan Kumar, An Overview on Productive Efficiency of Banks & Financial Institution (2018). International Journal of Research, Volume 05 Issue 12, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837503>
26. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Review on the Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country (2018). Journal for Studies in Management and Planning, Volume 04 Issue 05, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837496>
27. Basha, Jeelan and Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Performance Analysis of Financial Ratios - Indian Public Non-Life Insurance Sector (April 30, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837465>.
28. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, The Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country With Special Reference to Banks & Financial Institution (april 30, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844432> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844432>
29. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Study on Performance of Foreign Banks in India (APRIL 2, 2016).

Available at

SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844403> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844403>

30. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-Finance and the Financial Services Industry (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at

SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844405> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844405>

31. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-payment - An Overview (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844409> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844409> .

32. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Customer Satisfaction at M/s Sindol Bajaj Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4 ,Issue 12, June 2021, Page 157-169 Available at:
<https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702792.pdf>

33. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Ratio Analysis at NSSK, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 170-182 Available at:
<https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702793.pdf>

34. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Financial Statement Analysis of Shri Ram City Union Finance" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 183-196 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702794.pdf>

35. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Employee Job Satisfaction at Big Bazaar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 197-206 Available at:
<https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702795.pdf>

36. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Effect of Branding on Consumer Buying Behaviour at Vijay Bharat Motors Pvt Ltd, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 207-222 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702796.pdf>

37. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Customer Perceptions Guru Basava Motors, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 223-231 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/17027972.pdf>

38. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Loans and Advances for DCC Bank Main Branch Nayakaman, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 232-242 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702798.pdf>

39. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Work Life Balance of Employees at Karanja Industries Pvt Ltd, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 243-

254 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702799.pdf>

40. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Working Capital Management at TVS Motors, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 255-265 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702800.pdf>
41. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Testing Weak Form Efficiency of Indian Stock Market – An Empirical Study on NSE (April 30, 2021). Emerging Global Strategies for Indian Industry (ISBN: 978-81-910118-7-6), 2021, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837488>
42. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Top 10 Ways to Improve the Communication Skills (JUNE 20, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844410> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844410>
43. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Multi-Inter-Trans Disciplinary Research Towards Management and Commerce (July 25, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3847404>